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Electronic Payments System and Economic Growth in Nigeria

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Abstract

Over time, the way and manner goods and services are paid for have evolved dramatically from shells, to coins, to paper, to data capable of moving around the world in the blink of an eye. The role of electronic payments system in modern economy cannot be over-emphasized. Electronic payments are a key driver of the economy. Though the nexus between electronic payments system and economic performance has attracted attention from scholars and practitioners alike, very few studies have modeled this relationship correctly and comprehensively. This has resulted in a gap in the literature. This study, therefore, is designed to fill in this gap by investigating the relationship between electronic payments system and economic performance in Nigeria. The empirical data were collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria 2014 Statistical Bulletin and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings reveal that electronic payments system is positively correlated with economic performance. Results also show that external reserve is the dominant factor in the relationship with economic performance. The other factors influencing GDP show positive relationships with economic performance. The study was, however, limited by covering only six years in the selection of period of coverage, making this a possibly biased selection and it may not be adequate to generalize the results for the entire Nigeria economic performance. The study has contributed to the electronic payments system literature with a better understanding of the e-payment practices and their association with Nigeria's economic performance that will provide valuable knowledge to economic team top-management, to refine their current practices and subsequently improve the economic performance of Nigeria.

Keywords: *Central Bank of Nigeria, electronic payments system, economic performance, Nigeria.*

1. Introduction

Sustainable economic performance is at the heart of every responsible government financial and economic policies. The health of the economy is usually measured by its performance. Central to economic performance is the financial payment system in place. In the highly competitive marketplace, variety of Electronic Payments System (EPS) have been introduced to facilitate and fast track payments system. The electronic payments system plays a very crucial role in the economy, being the channel through which financial resources flow from one segment of the economy to the other. It therefore represents the major foundation of the modern economy.

In Nigeria, a number of these platforms include but not limited to Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Point of Sale (POS), Internet (web-based), Mobile Payment, NIBSS Instant Payment and NIBSS NEFT. Note that NIBSS stands for Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System and NEFT stands for NIBSS Electronic Fund Transfer. While ATM, POS, internet payment and mobile payment services have been available in Nigeria since 2006, NIBSS instant payment and NEFT were introduced in 2012. Nevertheless, the use of electronic payments system in Nigeria has increased tremendously. EPS is designed to offer efficient, reliable and secure payments system critical to

sound financial system, efficient financial markets, economic growth and development process. It is also designed to drive the engine of growth, reduce barriers to trade, increase geographical reach and increase capital flows. EPS is a tool for engaging more populace, creating additional savings, encourage movement from paper-based to electronic payment system and ensure global competitiveness.

EPS is designed to offer comfort from home, availability of banking services 24/7, efficiency, security, convenience and real time notifications. The CBN has placed the potential cost saving of between 50-70 per cent from economy of scale effects and reduced friction from electronic payments system. Furthermore, EPS enables commerce to operate more efficiently and this happens in four ways:

- (a) Convenient access to resources. EPS gives consumers immediate access to all of their financial resources – funds on deposit or a line of credit – to be used to pay when goods or services are required such as groceries or a taxi ride without stopping to visit an ATM;
- (b) Less cash at home. Most cash transactions create spare change that often leaves the economic system, driving down consumption. Card payments keep this money in consumers' accounts to be spent at a later date;
- (c) Reduces the gray economy. Cash payments are sometimes left undeclared as income by retailers. Cards can increase taxable income by creating an electronic audit trail; and
- (d) Reduced risk of fraud. Inherent in many electronic payment networks is the guarantee of payment for merchants and liability protection for cardholders in the case of fraud. These protections bolster confidence in the system, which can lead to greater overall consumption, particularly for high-value transactions.

However, despite these aforementioned benefits offered by EPS, the system is faced with inadequate ICT infrastructure, high cost of ICT deployment, slow internet connection, unexpected system failure, security, behavioural constraints and poor funding. It is in view of these challenges that this study examines the contributions of electronic payments system to the Nigerian economy. It is expected that given the rapid technological advancements and increasing consumer demand, positive transition towards increased acceptance of electronic payments system and channels will be the future of EPS in Nigeria. The prospects of EPS in Nigeria, notwithstanding, there are limited empirical studies that examined the contributions of EPS to the Nigerian economy. The few studies have yielded conflicting results: some support the hypothesis that investment in EPS is associated with a decline in economic performance. Others have found that EPS is associated positively with economic performance. Still other studies have found no significant relationship. In general, studies of the relationship between EPS and economic performance have not yielded robust results. It is as a result of this gap in the literature that this study is designed to examine the trends and effects of electronic payments system on economic performance in Nigeria. This also leads to the following hypothesis:

H₀: Electronic payments system has no significant effect on economic performance in Nigeria

2. Literature Review

This section covers the conceptual framework of the study, which graphically illustrates the relationship between electronic payments system and economic performance. The nexus between electronic payments system and economic performance is best illustrated using a conceptual framework. Talib, Rahman and Qureshi (2013), Park and Jang (2013), Nirajini and Priya (2013), Javed, Younas and Imran (2014), Yahaya, Farouk, Lamidi, Yusuf and Dania (2015), Yahaya, Kutigi, Solanke, Onyabe and Usman (2015) and Yahaya, Saheed, Farouk, Jimoh, Yusuf and Dania (2015) all use conceptual framework in their studies. The conceptual framework, which illustrates the nexus between electronic payments system and economic performance, is illustrated in figure 1 as follows:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework showing independent variable affecting dependent variable

An emerging economy is an economy with low to middle per capita income. Such economies constitute approximately 80% of the global population, and represent about 20% of the world's economies (Heakal, 2015). Although, the term is loosely used, countries that fall into this category, vary from very big to very small, and are usually considered emerging because of their level of development and reform. Hence, even though Nigeria is the largest economy in Africa, it is lumped into the category alongside much smaller economies with a great deal less resources, like Comoros, Sao Tome and Principe. Both Nigeria and Comoros belong to this category because both have embarked on economic development and reform programmes, and have begun to open up their markets and emerge onto the global scene. Emerging economies are considered to be fast-growing economies.

The commonest measure of economy regardless of the category it belongs is the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). GDP is the market value of all final goods and services from a nation in a given year. It is calculated without making deductions for depreciation of fabricated assets or for depletion and degradation of natural resources. It is one of the primary indicators used to gauge the health of a country's economy. It represents the total value of all goods and services produced over a specific time period. It simply measures the size of the economy. The average GDP for Nigeria over the period of study is ₦49,639.47 billion. Also, total GDP for the period is ₦446,755.25 billion. A major factor affecting GDP of a country is the payments system. The nature of payments constantly evolves for the most basic of reasons; human beings are innovative, resourceful and pragmatic. Humans embrace new techniques and technologies that offer greater efficiency, convenience and value creation and discard those that do not. The history of payments, the ways in which humans exchange value for goods and services has been dynamic, fluid and driven by the marketplace. Payments are the lifeblood of economies, whether emerging or developed. The widespread adoption of electronic payments has significantly expanded the value of goods and services sold, reduced the barriers to immediate credit and liquidity, and eased geographic restrictions to trade and exchange. The economic value of electronic payments has been measurable and substantial. The average value of EPS for the period under study is

₦10,040.78 billion. Also, the total value of electronic payments system for the period under study is ₦90,367.00 billion.

Visa (2003) examines a cross-section of 50 countries and concludes that increasing the existing share of electronic payments in a country by a margin of just 10 percent will generate an increase of 0.5 percent in consumer spending. The study further argues that in a country that has a 20 percent EPS share of US\$30 billion in consumer spending, enlarging that share to 22 percent will generate roughly US\$150 million in incremental consumer spending. Similarly, Moody (2009) examines the impact of digital currency on economic growth of 51 countries over a period of six years covering 2003-2008 and concludes that EPS delivered \$1.1 trillion to the global economy. This on average represents a 0.5 percent increase in total annual gross domestic product (GDP). However, during the same period, real global GDP grew by 3.4 percent. The study finds that, on average, increasing EPS usage by just 1 percent translates to a 0.024 percent increase in GDP. This equates to \$15 billion in additional GDP globally for every 1 percent increase. The study concludes that the availability of EPS is an important contributor to consumption and economic growth, and therefore recommends that access to EPS should be promoted worldwide. Umoren (2010) examines the impact of electronic banking on the Nigeria economy using a case study and concludes that e-banking has positively contributed to Nigeria economic growth.

Agbaje and Ayanbadejo (2013) examine the impact of e-payment on economic growth in Nigeria. The data employed for the analysis were both primary and secondary. The primary data was obtained through a questionnaire. The secondary data used in this study was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletins. The data was analyzed using specialized software- the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) ver. 17. The findings show that electronic payments system accounts for 3.1% of GDP over the study period (2006-2011). Similarly, Ozuru, Chikwe and Uduma (2013) investigate the use of traditional payments and electronic payments system in Nigeria and conclude that the use of electronic payment systems has gradually gained prominence.

Visa (2013) examines the use of electronic payments system and finds that EPS adds \$983 billion to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of 56 countries examined between 2008 and 2012. The study also finds that EPS usage in the U.S. increased consumption by 0.3 percent, adding \$127 billion to the U.S. economy; China by 4.89%; Chile by 1.28%; and Brazil by 1.15%. The study, therefore, concludes that increased credit and debit card usage contributes to economic activity by reducing transaction costs and improving efficiency in the flow of goods and services. The study also observes that electronic payments lead to a reduction in the gray economy by increasing transparency and generating additional tax revenue. Okoro (2014) examines the impact of selected e-payment instruments on the intermediation efficiency of the Nigerian economy using time series data of 2006 – 2011 and concludes that there is significant relationship between ATM, PoS, Internet service values and the intermediation efficiency of the of Nigerian economy.

Tijani and Ilugbemi (2015) examine the impact of electronic payments channels (EPC) on national development. The study reveals that electronic payment channels (EPC) have impacted on the economy and therefore contributing positively to national development (ND). They recommend that EPS should be promoted in Nigeria. Also, Okifo and Igbunu (2015) examine electronic

payments system in Nigeria, its economic benefits and challenges and conclude that the benefits of e-payment are unquantifiable as it has capacity to galvanize Nigeria into a cashless society.

3. Methodology

Data was collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletins covering a period of nine years (2006 – 2014). Note that electronic payments system begins in Nigeria in 2006. Also, data on EPS for 2015 is not available in the 2015 CBN Statistical Bulletin. This explains the reason why the period of coverage is limited to 2006-2014. The following regression equation was estimated and tested:

$$\ln\text{GDP}_t = \alpha + \beta_1\ln\text{EPS}_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Whereas:

ln = Logarithm normal used to transform data to control for normality and heteroskedasticity.

GDP = Gross Domestic Product, used to proxy economic performance (Kira, 2013; Yahaya, 2014; De Haas & Van Lelyveld, 2014; Kanu & Ozurumba, 2014; Yahaya, 2015 and Yahaya, Saheed, Farouk, Jimoh, Yusuf & Dania, 2015).

α , β_{1-4} = constant and beta coefficients, respectively

EPS = Electronic Payments System (aggregate values of transactions through ATM, PoS, Internet, Mobile pay, NIBSS and NEFT)

ε = stochastic error term

t = time script (9 years in this case)

Consistent with previous literatures, the study used GDP as a measure of economic performance. The data on the variables are provided by RTC Advisory Services Ltd for the period 2006-2008 and the Central Bank of Nigeria for the period 2009-2014. As per the stated hypothesis, the study predicts a positive relationship between EPS and GDP.

4. Results and Discussion

The results of the study are reported in this section. They include the results of normal distribution test, descriptive statistics, trends analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis and post estimation tests.

4.1 Test for Data Normality

The test for data normality was carried out using Shapiro-Wilk test. The results of the normality test after transformation using logarithm normal (ln) are reported in table 1 as follows:

Table 1 Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
logGDP	9	0.85403	2.145	1.388	0.08251
logEPS	9	0.88695	1.661	0.894	0.18560

Source: STATA 13 Output based on study data

From table 1, the values of Prob>z are greater than 0.05 and therefore, it can be concluded that the data are normally distributed and also free of heteroskedasticity problem.

4.2 Summary Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics are commonly used for summarizing measures of central tendency such as the median, range, mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum. Summary descriptive statistics of interest to this study are presented in table 2 as follows:

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
logGDP	9	10.64535	.637197	9.829011	11.39688
logEPS	9	7.360754	2.318989	4.460145	10.57005

Source: STATA 13 Output based on study data

From table 2, the number of observations is 9 and the mean value of GDP over the study period is about 10.65. Similarly, the average value of EPS over the study period is about 7.36. EPS low mean value may be explained by the fact that EPS is a recent phenomenon in Nigeria, having commenced in 2006 with ATM, PoS, Internet and mobile pay, while Instant pay and NEFT commenced in 2012.

4.3 Trend Analysis of EPS and Economic Performance

Table 3 shows a line graph illustrating the trends of electronic payments system and economic performance in Nigeria. Note that the values of EPS and GDP have been logged to base normal in order to ensure normality and eliminate heteroskedasticity problem.

Source: MS Excel 2007 Output based on study data

4.4 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis shows relationship between two or more variables in a study. Table 4 reports the results of the correlation analysis as follows:

Table 4 Correlation Coefficients

Variable	logGDP	logEPS
logGDP	1.0000	
logEPS	0.8906	1.0000

Source: STATA 13 Output based on study data

From table 4, the relationship between electronic payments system and economic performance is positive and strong (0.8906). This result is very important and is consistent with extant literature. The result is also in agreement with the study priori expectation.

4.5 Effect of Electronic Payments System on Economic Performance

The core research question in this study is to assess whether electronic payments system leads to lower or higher economic performance. This effect is best illustrated in tables 5 and 6 as follows:

Table 5 Model Summary and Analysis of Variance

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	9
Model	2.57647358	1	2.57647358	F(1, 7)	26.85
Residual	.671686407	7	.095955201	Prob > F	0.0013
				R-squared	0.7932
Total	3.24815999	8	.406019998	Adj R-squared	0.7637
				Root MSE	.30977

Source: STATA 13 Output based on study data

From table 5, the number of observations is 9. The F statistic value is 26.85 and the F probability value which tests for analysis of variance is 0.0013, which implies very strong statistical significance of the overall model. The R^2 is 0.7932 and the adjusted R^2 is 0.7637, which implies that about 76.37 per cent of the variations in economic performance are explained by electronic payments system. Similarly, Cohen’s rule for effect size is used to test the effect size of the model. According to Cohen (1988), R^2 between 1.0 and 5.9 percent is considered as small, between 5.9 and 13.8 percent is medium, and above 13.8 percent is large. From table 5, it can be observed that R^2 is 0.7932, thus, the effect size for this study is large.

Table 6 Regression Matrix

logGDP	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf.	Interval]
logEPS	.2447198	.047227	5.18	0.001	.1330457	.356394
_cons	8.844026	.3626374	24.39	0.000	7.986525	9.701527

Source: STATA 13 Output based on study data

From table 6, the t test is used to test for the significance of the explanatory variable. The calculated t-test value for logEPS is 5.18 while its associated p-value is 0.001. Since the p-value of logEPS is less than the chosen level of significance 0.05 (5%), the null hypothesis (H_0) which states that electronic payments system has no significant effect on economic performance is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. This means that electronic payments system has significant effect on economic performance in Nigeria. It should be noted that the significant effect EPS has on economic performance is positive ($\beta = .2447198$), which is in line with priori expectation. This result is also in agreement with the studies by Okoro (2014) and Tijani and Ilugbemi (2015).

4.6 Autocorrelation Test

The Durbin Watson Statistic is a number that tests for autocorrelation in the residuals from a statistical regression analysis. The Durbin-Watson statistic is always between 0 and 4; a value of 2 means that there is no autocorrelation in the sample. Values approaching 0 indicate positive autocorrelation and values toward 4 indicate negative autocorrelation. The result of the test for autocorrelation using the Durbin-Watson statistics is reported in table 7.

Table 7 Durbin-Watson Index		
Durbin-Watson	d-statistic(2, 9) =	1.564794
Source: STATA 13 Output based on study data		

From table 7, the Durbin-Watson index is about 1.565 suggests that there is no serious autocorrelation problem in the study.

4.7 Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity occurs when the error variance has non-constant variance. Stated equivalently, the variance of the observed value of the dependent variable around the regression line is non-constant. In this study, the Breusch-Pagan test for heteroskedasticity was carried and the results are reported in table 8.

Table 8 Breusch-Pagan test for Heteroskedasticity	
. hetttest	
Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity	
Ho: Constant variance	
Variables: fitted values of logGDP	
chi ² (1) = 0.76	
Prob > chi ² = 0.3839	
Source: STATA 13 based on the study data	

In testing for heteroskedasticity with Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test, if the probability (p-value) > 0.05, then there is no problem of heteroskedasticity, however, if the probability value < 0.05, then there is a problem of heteroskedasticity. From table 8, the chi² probability value is 0.3839, which is greater than 0.05, meaning that there is no heteroskedasticity problem in the study data.

4.8 Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test

In order to determine whether the variables follow a unit root, the study carried out the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test and the results are reported in table 9.

Table 9 Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test	
No. of observations	9
logGDP	0.8608

logEPS 0.9263
Source: STATA 13 based on the study data

The null hypothesis is that the variable contains a unit root, and the alternative is that the variable was generated by a stationary process. From table 9, the Z(t) scores for logGDP and logEPS are greater than 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis which states that the variables exhibit a unit root is accepted.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has achieved its objectives having analyzed the trends, association between and effects of electronic payments system on economic performance in Nigeria. The study finds electronic payments system to have significant and positive effect on the Nigerian economy. The study provides a useful framework for understanding electronic payments system and economic performance nexus in Nigeria. With regard to the policy implications, the findings suggest that electronic payments system improves the performance of the economy. There is need therefore for more investments in EPS platforms in order to see the many benefits of electronic payments system in Nigeria.

In addition, the findings of this study serve as valuable guides to scholars, managers of the economy and other stakeholders. This study offers immense relevance for understanding the effectiveness of electronic payments system–economic performance discourse. However, a great deal more of insightful and detailed research would be required to extend the conclusions of this study, having regard to the fact that electronic payments system is relatively new in Nigeria. The following refinements and extensions of the present problem may thus be undertaken. In the future, a large time series data may be included in the study. As electronic payments system-economic performance is a major issue for research, more variables that affect economic performance can also be studied. These results also highlight the importance to managers of the Nigerian economy of studying fundamentals of EPS-economic performance, while from a economic management perspective, effective management of EPS can increase growth. Also, the economic implications of moving to a more efficient, secure and transparent methods of payment are important considerations for policymakers around the world.

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